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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ADAPTED TEXTS IN ENHANCING VOCABULARY ACQUISITION FOR FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNERS

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Abstract

This paper investigates the influence of adapted texts on foreign language learners' vocabulary acquisition by comparing the results of reading an authentic version of Charles Dicken' novel "Oliver Twist" (Group A) and an adapted version (Group B). The study examines the benefits of using adapted texts in foreign language classes in terms of time efficiency, vocabulary enrichment, plot comprehension and learner motivation. Throughout the study, both groups received the same instructions and assessment methods to ensure fairness and accuracy in the assessment process. These results show several advantageous aspects of using adapted texts in foreign language learning. First, the adapted text significantly accelerated the learning process, allowing Group B to cover a wider vocabulary range in a shorter amount of time. In addition, Group B showed a significant increase in vocabulary recall compared to Group A, suggesting that the adapted text provides ample opportunities to learn new vocabulary in one class.

Keywords: vocabulary acquisition, new words, adapted text, authentic text, reading.

Vocabulary acquisition plays a crucial role in the process of mastering a foreign language. After all, insufficient vocabulary can create serious obstacles to communicating in the target language. Speaking of the significance of vocabulary acquisition, Schmitt highlights that "lexical knowledge" is central to the development of communicative competence. [1] Wilkins argues that grammatical sentences cannot be made without the words to be communicated in the message. Thus, grammar, syntactics, and other aspects that should be learned in the process of language acquisition are not as effective in the absence of vocabulary. [2] In general, devoting attention to vocabulary development should be the main goal of foreign language teaching to achieve the successful communicative competence.

Vocabulary enrichment can take place through reading, which is the most traditional way of developing lexical knowledge. According to Krashen, reading is considered as effective tools for vocabulary enrichment. [3] Learning a new word while reading a text helps students not just learn the meaning and translation of a word, but also its meaning in different contexts which helps in different communicative events. [4]

When choosing a text for a foreign language lesson, one must choose between authentic and adapted material, which have their advantages and disadvantages. Authentic text came from a style of teaching called "authentic learning", developed in the 1990s and aimed at building authentic communicative and cultural competence in learners. By authentic text, Valdeón García means "material produced by native speakers, created for both native speakers and language learners that sounds natural in real-life communication". [5] And adapted texts are texts modified for methodologi-

cal purposes in the direction of simplification, highlighting certain characteristics of the text. Adapted texts can be simplified or complicated according to the learners' level of language competence. [6]

In most cases of using texts to teach a foreign language, the choice always falls on adapted texts rather than authentic texts. So why choose adapted texts over authentic texts? There are several reasons for not using authentic texts and using adapted texts in language classroom:

- The differences between cultures of target language and learners' culture. Some aspects of the target language's culture may be unacceptable to the learners or even opposite to each other.
- The language units in authentic materials may not correspond to the students' language proficiency level and develop some complexity, which leads to a decrease in the motivational period of learning.
- Selecting the suitable authentic texts for the lesson requires a lot of time and effort.
- Fast obsolescence of information, lack of relevance when working with news materials.
- Authentic text may contain grammatical structure that is overly complex for learners.

These shortcomings are the main reasons of applying adapted texts instead the use of authentic one.

Do adapted texts help learners acquire vocabulary more effectively and faster than authentic texts? In this research paper, we will study the use of adapted texts in the process of vocabulary acquisition by conducting an experiment involving a comparison of the application of authentic and adapted texts in a foreign language class.

To investigate how effective adapted texts are in learning new words through reading, we conducted an experiment on 18 students of the Kazakh National University named after Al-Farabi in specialty “Foreign languages: two foreign languages”, divided into two groups (A and B) of equally 9 people with intermediate level. The first group was provided with authentic texts and the second group with adapted texts of the same text to demonstrate a distinct difference in results.

As the main material for the experiment, we selected Charles Dickens’ literary work “Oliver Twist” (1 & 2 chapter), the original and adapted versions from the website “Adapted Books in English”. Group “A” worked with the original version and the second group “B” received the adapted version of this book according to their intermediate language proficiency level. There are 5 stages in the practical part:

1. Reading the book chapter by chapter
2. Listing unknown words

3. Memorizing unfamiliar words by demonstrating translation and examples with sentences.

4. Checking the assimilation of new vocabulary

5. Taking a quiz on the plot of the chapter

“A group” results.

“A” group consists of 9 students with intermediate proficiency level, and they were provided with the original version of the first and second chapter. In the first stage of the experiment, the 1st chapter of the book “Treats of the place where Oliver Twist was born and of the circumstances attending his birth”, consisting of 1100 words, was read. In total, students spent more than 30-32 minutes reading the chapter and approximately reread it 8-9 times.

The second stage was spent on listing the unknown words of the chapter. Overall, the number of unknown words was 116 which is the 10,5 percent of the text. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Number of unknown words encountered by each student.

Over 30 minutes were spent demonstrating the translation of 116 words and another 25 minutes showing them in context. In the process of vocabulary acquisition, students were bored already after 13-14 words and lacked sufficient motivation to continue learning.

The next stage was to check vocabulary acquisition 116 new words, the format of the test was simple: students had to match translations of the given words. The results were not satisfactory, the average result was 40 out of 116. The highest point was 58 (Student 7), and the lowest was 27 (Student 3). (Figure 2)

Figure 2. The result of each student. (Out of 116 words)

Once students were familiarized with the new words, they read the first chapter again to check how well they understood the plot of the chapter. The students read the chapter for about 17 minutes and then

took a test consisting of 14 questions. They spent 18 minutes on the test, and the result was unsatisfactory - the average score was 4, highest score is 7, lowest score is 3. (Figure 3)

Figure 3. The results of each student. (Out of 14 point)

“B” group results.

Group “B” consists of 9 students with intermediate language proficiency who were given an adapted version of "Oliver Twist" from the “Adapted Books in English” website. The first chapter, "Early Days," is

832 words and students spent 15 minutes to read it. Following this, students list the unknown words from the chapter, totaling 21 words which is 2,5 percent of the text. (Figure 4)

Figure 4. The number of unfamiliar words each student has.

Another 15 minutes were spent on demonstrating the translation of unfamiliar words out of context and in context. During the explanation, students showed interest and asked additional questions regarding the new vocabulary, also no decrease in motivation and interest was noticed.

The next stage of the experiment was to examine the assimilation of new vocabulary, the format of which was the same as in group “A” - matching words with their translation. The result of the examination was good and satisfactory, the average result was 19, the highest result is 21 (Student 3 & 6), the lowest is 16 (Student 2). (Figure 5)

Figure 5. Vocabulary acquisition testing results. (Out of 21 words)

Following the vocabulary check, students read the chapter again for 10 minutes to take the chapter plot quiz, which is the final stage of the experiment. The

quiz consists of 14 questions and students spent 12 minutes to complete it. The result was absolutely what we expected, the average score was 12, the highest

score was 14 (Student 3 & 7) and the lowest was 9 (Student 2). (Figure 6)

Figure 6. The quiz result of each student (Out of 14 point)

Comparison of "A" group and "B" group results.

1. The amount of new vocabulary.

In accordance with Ronald P. Carver, the percentage of unknown words in one text should be 2-3 % which is enough to keep the motivation of students and enrich vocabulary from one text. [7] The authentic version of the first chapter of "Treats of the place where Oliver Twist was born and of the circumstances attending his birth" contains 1,100 words in which 116 words are new to students, representing 10.5% of the text. The adapted version of the first chapter "Early days" for

group "B" consists of 832 words, in which 21 words are unfamiliar to students, which is 2.5% of the text meeting the abovementioned requirements.

2. How many new words did students acquire from each version of Chapter One?

From the results of group "A", on average, students memorized only 40 words out of 116 new words, which is 34% of new vocabulary. Group "B" memorized about 19 words which is the 90 % of 21 new words from the adapted first chapter. (Figure 7)

Figure 7. The percentage relativity of learned and unlearned words from each group for the first chapter.

If we look at the number of words learned, we can say that there are more words learned from the authentic text than from the adapted text. But by memorizing only 34% of the new words in the authentic text, even if there were more words, the student would not be able to fully understand the text, while there were 21 new words in the adapted text, and the students memorized these 21 words, which helped them understand the plot of the first chapter.

3. Comparison of plot quiz results of both groups.

Students from "A" and "B" group take a quiz regarding the plot of the chapter after they get acquainted with new words from the text. Group A's average score (4 points) was significantly lower than Group B's quiz scores (12 points). Group A's highest score was 7 points and Group B's best score was 14 out of 14 points. The difference in low scores is very large which is 3 (group A) and 9 (group B). (Figure 8)

Figure 8. Comparative indicator of the performance of the two groups on the story comprehension test.

4. Time spent over the stages of experiment.

In total, group “A” spent over 132 minutes (2 hours 12 minutes) on reading, learning vocabulary, and taking the quiz, while the “B group” spent only 62 minutes (1 hour 2 minutes) to complete given assignments. Looking at the time spent, it is safe to say that learning new vocabulary by reading an adapted text will save time, while working with a single text for

more than two hours will lead to a loss of motivation, concentration and focus on the target task. On Figure 9 shown the times spent on each stage of the experiment. Looking at this chart, it is safe to say that acquiring and testing vocabulary through reading authentic text can be a laborious process that will take an inordinate amount of time.

Figure 9. Time spent on each stage of the experiment (minutes)

Conclusion. In conclusion, this paper has investigated and substantiated the effectiveness of using adapted texts to improve the efficiency of vocabulary acquisition by foreign language learners. Through a comprehensive analysis of the advantages of adapted texts over authentic texts, it is evident that adapting materials can be a very beneficial approach for foreign language learners.

The first big advantage of using adapted texts is the time saving. Simplifying language and content allows students to learn new vocabulary and language structures more efficiently. This allows students to master the material more quickly, which ultimately accelerates their overall language proficiency. The time saved can be used for other language activities, ensuring a more balanced and integrated language acquisition process.

Another indisputable advantage of edited texts is that they are not too complex. Unlike authentic texts, which often contain a huge amount of linguistic nuance and cultural references, adapted texts strike a fine balance between complexity and clarity. Learners can immerse themselves in meaningful and relevant content without feeling overwhelmed or frustrated. As a result, the process of vocabulary acquisition is smoother and more enjoyable, fostering curiosity and a desire to learn the language further.

Last, but not least, motivation plays a key role in the language learning process, and adapted texts can greatly increase learners' enthusiasm. When learners are exposed to texts adapted to their current language ability, they experience a sense of satisfaction and confidence when they successfully understand and master the material. This positive reinforcement serves as a

strong motivational factor that encourages learners to persist in language learning and move on to more challenging texts when their proficiency level increases.

However, it is important to note that adapted texts should not be considered as a complete substitute for authentic materials. Although they play an important role in vocabulary acquisition, contact with authentic texts is still necessary for the development of cultural understanding, critical thinking, and linguistic competence.

In general, the effectiveness of adapted texts in increasing the efficiency of vocabulary acquisition by language learners is unquestionable. Saving time, increasing motivation and the optimal level of difficulty of such materials contribute to more effective and enjoyable language learning. Teachers and learners should consider using adapted texts as a valuable resource in their language learning programs, thus creating an environment conducive to continued growth and linguistic success.

References

1. Schmitt, N. (2000). *Vocabulary in language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
2. MOFAREH ALQAHTANI (2015). The importance of vocabulary in language learning and how to be taught . *International Journal of Teaching and Education*, Vol. III(3), pp. 21-34. , DOI: 10.52950/TE.2015.3.3.002
3. Krashen, S. (1989). We acquire vocabulary and spelling by reading: Additional evidence for the input hypothesis. *The Modern Language Journal*, 73(4), 440-464.
4. Ellis, N. C. (1994). Vocabulary acquisition: The implicit ins and outs of explicit cognitive mediation. In N. C. Ellis (Ed.), *Implicit and explicit learning of languages* (pp. 211-282). San Diego, CA: Academic Press.
5. Valdeón García, R.A. 1995. "A Redefinition of Authentic Material and its Use in the Teaching of English". *Revista Canaria de Estudios Ingleses*. Universidad de La Laguna: Tenerife. Volumen nº 30/31, p.227-239
6. *New Dictionary of Methodological Terms and Concepts (Theory and Practice of Language Teaching)*. - Moscow: ICAR Publishing House. E. G. Azimov, A. N. Shchukin. 2009.
7. Carver, R. P. (1994). Percentage of Unknown Vocabulary Words in Text as a Function of the Relative Difficulty of the text: Implications for Instruction. *Journal of Reading Behavior*, 26(4), 413-437. doi:10.1080/10862969409547861